

The Analysis of Regressive Factor at Employee Performance of RSGM Jember University

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Abstract:- The aims of study were to analyze the factors that affect the performance of the employees of the RSGM Jember University. This study uses a quantitative approach, the type of analytic observational research with a cross sectional research design. The number of samples was 97. The data were analyzed using the Spearman correlation test and ordinal logistic regression. The variables in this study include the characteristics of the respondents (gender, age, education level and years of service), leadership style, work discipline and training. This research has conducted an ethical test with the number 1403/UN25.8/KEPK/DL/2021. The results showed that there was an influence between gender, age, years of service, work discipline and training on the performance of the employees of RSGM Universitas Jember. The results showed that there was no influence between the level of education and leadership style on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University. The most influential factor on the performance of the employees of the University of Jember is work discipline.

Keywords:- characteristics, leadership style, work discipline, training, performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Dental and Oral Hospital (RSGM) of the University of Jember is a health institution that provides dental and oral health services which has been established since December 10, 2005. RSGM is a means of education and research within the University of Jember. In addition to focusing on providing maximum service. RSGM is also a learning tool so that it is necessary to implement good employee and student performance so that they are optimal in providing services to the community. RSGM is in the process of preparing accreditation for hospitals so that several requirements are needed based on PMK No. 4 of 2019 concerning technical standards for fulfilling basic service quality at minimum service standards in the health sector. Employee performance can be measured from several indicators given to patients. Completeness of documents, patient waiting time and patient satisfaction. This can be measured as the performance of hospital employees to monitor how the performance of each department in the hospital. RSGM performance can be measured based on the completeness of the records of each section from administration to medical records. Based on secondary data, it shows that there is an increase in the percentage of patient waiting time (>60 minutes) during the last 3 months, namely September by 12%, October by 32%, and November by 61%. Patient waiting time shows the employee's performance in dealing with patients. Another

indicator based on completeness of documents also experienced an increase in the percentage that did not fill in the accuracy of patient identification consisting of the patient's name and date of birth during the last 3 months. September is 30%, October is 34%, and November is 68%. Kefina (2015) shows that employee performance is measured by the quality of nursing care provided to patients. Bawono and Nugraheni (2015) show that the performance appraisal of employees at the Semarang City Hospital uses primary data that is asked directly to patients. Muntaha (2017) shows the performance measurement of hospital employees at RSUD Soedarso Pontianak based on primary data obtained from patient complaints directly or through the suggestion box provided by the hospital. Kefina (2015) shows that employee performance is measured by the quality of nursing care provided to patients. Bawono and Nugraheni (2015) show that the performance appraisal of employees at the Semarang City Hospital uses primary data that is asked directly to patients. Muntaha (2017) shows the performance measurement of hospital employees at RSUD Soedarso Pontianak based on primary data obtained from patient complaints directly or through the suggestion box provided by the hospital. Kefina (2015) shows that employee performance is measured by the quality of nursing care provided to patients. Bawono and Nugraheni (2015) show that the performance appraisal of employees at the Semarang City Hospital uses primary data that is asked directly to patients. Muntaha (2017) shows the performance measurement of hospital employees at RSUD Soedarso Pontianak based on primary data obtained from patient complaints directly or through the suggestion box provided by the hospital.

Performance is influenced by several factors including leadership style, work discipline and training. Based on secondary data obtained from the staffing center of the University of Jember, at RSGM approximately 54.7% of employees arrived late on work shifts. The average employee tardiness exceeds 30 minutes from the shift schedule, including: 1). Morning shift 07.30 – 15.00; 2). Afternoon 14.30 – 22.00; 3). Night 21.30 – 07.30. According to the Ministry of PANRB (State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform), employees are said to be late if they exceed 30 minutes from the start of the work shift. The impact of work discipline problems affects patient waiting time which affects services at the RSGM. Tumilar (2015) shows that leadership style, work discipline and work motivation simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance, leadership style and work discipline partially affect employee performance. Muis et al. (2021) partially shows that the variables of motivation, work discipline and leadership style have a positive and significant

effect on employee performance. While the independent variables of motivation, work discipline and leadership style simultaneously have a significant relationship with the dependent variable of employee performance (Tumilaar, 2015; Muis, Kamal and Frandika, 2021)

The aims of study included 1) analyzing the effect of respondent characteristics (gender, age, education and years of service) on the performance of the employees of the RSGM Universitas Jember; 2) analyze The Effect of leadership style on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University; 3) analyzing work discipline on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University; 4) analyzing the training on the performance of the employees of the RSGM Jember University and 5) analyzing the factors that most influence the performance of the employees of the RSGM at the University of Jember.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

A. Leadership and Leadership Style

Stogdill in Sitepu et al. (2020) explains that leadership must involve other people, leadership includes an unequal distribution of power between leaders and group members, and leaders are legally able to give orders or directions to subordinates or followers. Handayani et al. (2020) explains that leadership is a process of one's activities to move others by leading, guiding, influencing others, to do something in order to achieve the expected results. According to Sembiring (2013), leadership style is a way used by leaders in interacting with their subordinates. Another opinion states that leadership style is a pattern of behavior (words and actions) of a leader that is felt by others (Sembiring, 2013; Putra and M, 2020)

The types of leadership styles according to House in Gusti (2019) are as follows:

- Directive Leadership Style
This leadership style allows subordinates to know what the leader expects of them, schedules work to be done, and provides specific guidance on how to complete tasks.
- Supportive Leadership Style
This leadership style is friendly and shows the needs of subordinates
- Participative Leadership Style
This leadership style consults with subordinates and uses their suggestions before making a decision
- Achievement Oriented Leadership Style
This leadership style sets challenging goals to achieve at the highest level (Gusti, 2019).

According to Kartono in Harahap, Nadra and Aginta (2021) a leader can be seen through indicators, including:

- Decision making ability
Decision making is a systematic approach to the nature of the alternatives faced and taking the action that according to calculations is the most appropriate action
- Motivational ability
The ability of motivation is a driving force that causes members of an organization to be willing and willing to move their abilities (in the form of expertise or skills) their energy and time to carry out various activities that are their

responsibility and fulfill their obligations in the context of achieving predetermined organizational goals and objectives.

- Communication skills
Communication ability is the ability or ability to deliver messages. Ideas, or thoughts to others with the aim of those other people understanding what is meant well. Directly or indirectly
- Ability to control subordinates
A leader must have the desire to make others follow his wishes by using personal power or position power effectively and in place for the long-term interests of the company. The terms include telling the other person what to do in tones varying from a firm tone to begging or even threatening. The goal is that the tasks can be completed properly.
- Responsibility
Responsibility is one of the factors that must be owned by a leader. Which is interpreted as an obligation to bear, take responsibility, bear everything or give responsibility and bear the consequences
- Ability to control emotions
The ability to control emotions is very important for a leader, because the better the leader's ability to control emotions, the more respected employees are. (Harahap, Nadra and Aginta, 2021).

Siagian in Zainal et al. (2019) Employee discipline is a form of training that seeks to improve and shape employee knowledge, attitudes and behavior so that these employees voluntarily try to work cooperatively with other employees and improve their work performance. (Zainal et al., 2019).

B. Work Discipline

According to Siswanto (2015) states there are 5 factors of work discipline, including:

- Attendance frequency
One of the benchmarks to determine the level of discipline of employees. The higher the frequency of attendance or the low level of absenteeism, the employee has high work discipline
- Alert level
Employees who in carrying out their work are always full of calculations and accuracy have a high level of vigilance towards themselves and their work.
- Adherence to work standards
Compliance with work standards, in carrying out their work employees are required to comply with all work standards that have been set in accordance with work rules and guidelines so that work accidents do not occur or can be avoided.
- Compliance with work regulations
Intended for convenience and smooth working
- work ethic
It is needed by every employee in carrying out their work in order to create a harmonious atmosphere, mutual respect between fellow employees (Silvya, 2019).

Indicators that affect the level of discipline of employees in the company, including:

- Goals and abilities

- Exemplary leadership
- remuneration
- Justice
- Waskat
- Penalty sanction
- Firmness
- Human relations

According to Rivai (2013) explains that many indicators affect the level of discipline of employees of an organization, including:

- Attendance rate
The number of employee attendance to carry out work activities in the company which is marked by the low level of employee attendance
- Obedience to superiors
Obedience to superiors is following what is directed by superiors in order to get good results
- Work awareness
The attitude of a person voluntarily doing his job well, not because of coercion
- Responsibility
Willingness of employees to be responsible for the results of their work, the facilities and infrastructure used and their work behavior (Rivai, 2013; Ichsan, Surianta and Nasution, 2020).

C. Training

The training needs analysis, involves three analytical activities, including:

- Organizational/environmental/Country analysis
This analysis is used to analyze the long, medium and short term plans of the MEA
- Job/task analysis
This task analysis begins with examining the description of a position/position, then followed by research on job requirements to carry out the duties of the position.
- Individual analysis
This individual analysis seeks to answer the question of who needs training and what kind of training is needed.

D. Employee Evaluation

To find out the level of success of a training program organized by an organization is very important, because it can be known whether the methods, materials and instructors used are effective or not. According to Fajar (2013), mentioning the sources of weakness in the implementation of training programs and evaluating the implementation of training programs can be identified. Among other things, reactions, learning, behavior and results (Dawn and Al, 2013).

E. Performance

The definition of performance according to Faustinu Cardosa Gomes in Fajrin (2018) suggests the definition of "employee performance as "expressions such as output, efficiency and effectiveness are often associated with productivity. Furthermore, the definition of employee performance (work achievement) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. A good organization is one that has succeeded in

achieving its vision, mission and goals. Performance Objectives, including:

- Proficiency from new task abilities is intended to improve performance results and activities
- Proficiency of new knowledge which will help employees with complex problem solving activities on decision making tasks
- Proficiency or improvement in attitudes towards coworkers with a performance activity
- Performance improvement activity targets
- Improvements in quality or production
- Repair in time or delivery (Rivai and Mulyadi, 2012).

F. Organizational Behavior Theory

According to Robbins and Judge (2014) organizational behavior is a field of study that investigates The Effect that individuals, groups, and structures have on behavior in organizations with the aim of applying this kind of knowledge to increase the effectiveness of an organization. (Robbins and Judge, 2014). According to George & Jones in Purba et al. (2020) organizational behavior is a study of various factors that influence the actions of individuals and groups in organizations and how organizations manage. The organizational behavior model has 3 sub-fields of organizational behavior that are developing, namely:

- Microorganizational behavior
Microorganizational behavior is related to the behavior of individuals who work.
- Meso organizational behavior
Meso organizational behavior is related to understanding the behavior of individuals who work together in teams or groups.
- Macro organizational behavior
Macro organizational behavior focuses on understanding organizational behavior as a whole.

The combination of organizational behavior theory and Gibson's (1991) theory which states that employee performance (individual performance) is influenced by several variables including individual, psychological and organizational variables. Individual variables consist of demographic factors including age, gender, years of service and training. Psychological variables consist of motivation, education and work discipline. Organizational variables consisting of HR (human resources), leadership, work structure, work design and incentives. Individual variables consisting of demographic factors including age, gender, years of service and training can affect employee performance. Based on the research of Hirarto et al. (2021) stated that the respondents' socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, (Hirarto et al., 2021). Training can be defined as an organized, planned and operational activity designed to change employee attitudes and behavior. Training can also be used to improve and modify skills, to align the organization's values, goals and objectives to achieve higher productivity. In line with the research of Yusnita and Fadhil (2015) which states that training has a positive influence on employee performance (Yusnita and Fadhil, 2015; Khan and Iqbal, 2020).

Psychological variables consisting of motivation, level of education and work discipline can affect employee performance. Based on Subariyanti's research (2017), it states that there is a positive and significant relationship between work motivation and the performance of PTLR Batan employees. Another study conducted by Jaya and Ningsih (2016) stated that there was a real relationship between work motivation and employee performance. Job satisfaction has an important role in supporting the achievement of organizational goals. Employee discipline factors that are not good will affect performance. In line with the research of Damayanty, Marjuni, and Ruslan (2018) which states that work discipline has an influence on employee performance. This means that the better the work discipline, the better the employee's performance (Damayanty, Marjuni and Ruslan, 2019). Organizational variables consist of HR, leadership, structure, work design and incentives factors. According to research by Kefina (2015) stated that HR, leadership, structure, work design and incentives factors have an influence on employee performance in hospitals. (Kefina, 2015). Good leadership will affect the results of good performance output as well. Another study conducted by Turang, Kindangen, Tumiwa, (2015) stated that either partially or simultaneously there is an influence between leadership style on employee performance. This means that the better the leadership style will affect employee performance (Turang, Kindangen and Tumiwa, 2015; Matte, 2017)

The hypothesis in this study is as follows:

- There is an influence between the characteristics of the respondents (gender, age, education level and years of service) on the performance of employees at the RSGM Universitas Jember
- There is an influence between leadership style on employee performance at RSGM Universitas Jember
- There is an influence between work discipline on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember
- There is an influence between training on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember

- There is the most influential factor between leadership style, work discipline and training on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember

III. METHODS

This study used a quantitative approach, the type of analytic observational research with the design or research design used is cross sectional. The research was conducted at the RSGM Universitas Jember in November – December 2021. The population in this study were all employees of the RSGM Universitas Jember. The sampling technique used is probability sampling with the type of simple random sampling according to Lemeshow (1997) the results obtained are 97. Survey of respondent data is carried out in two ways, including interviews with respondents and documentation in the form of images in the form of reports and information that can support research.

The variables in this study include the characteristics of the respondents including gender, age, education level, years of service, leadership style, work discipline and training. The analysis test consisted of univariate, bivariate and multivariate. Bivariate analysis using Spearman correlation test, multivariate analysis using ordinal logistic regression. This research has conducted an ethical test with the number 1403/UN25.8/KEPK/DL/2021

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Employee Characteristics on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

a) The Effect of Gender on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Gender distribution shows that most of the respondents are male as many as 43 people (44.3%). Female respondents were 54 people (55.7%). The analysis of the effect of gender on employee performance at the RSGM Jember University will be presented in Table 1.

Variable	Not enough		Performance Currently		Well		Total		p-value
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Gender									
Man	6	6.1	23	23.7	14	14.4	43	44.3	0.000*
Woman	4	4.1	32	32.9	18	18.5	54	55.6	
Total	10	10.3	55	56.7	32	32.9	97	100	

Table 1: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Gender on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas ember

Table 1 shows the results of cross tabulation that most women have moderate performance as many as 32 people (32.9%). The results of statistical tests using the chi-square test showed a p-value of 0.000, meaning that the p-value <0.05, which means the test results are significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between gender on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

b) Effect of Age on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The age distribution shows the majority of respondents that most of the respondents aged 31-40 years are 46 people (47.4%). The analysis of the effect of age on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember will be presented in Table 2.

Variable	Not enough		Performance Currently		Well		Total		p -value
	n	%	N	%	n	%	n	%	
Age									
21-30 Years	2	2.1	12	12.3	8	8.2	22	22.6	0.041*
31-40 Years	3	3.1	23	23.8	20	20.6	46	47.5	
>41 Years	5	5.1	20	20.7	4	4.1	4	29.9	
Total	10	10.3	55	56.8	32	32.9	32	100	

Table 2: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Age on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 2 shows the results of the cross tabulation that most of the respondents aged 31 - 40 years have moderate performance as many as 23 people (23.8%). The results of statistical tests using the Spearman correlation test showed a p-value of 0.041, meaning $p < 0.05$, which means the test results are significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between age on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

c) The Effect of Education Level on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The distribution of education level shows that most of the respondents graduated from Bachelor (S1)/Master (S2)/Doctorate (S3) as many as 47 people (48.5%). Analysis of the effect of education level on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember will be presented in Table 3

Variable	Not enough		Performance Currently		Well		Total		p -value
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Level of education									
finished high school	0	0	4	4.1	0	0	4	4.1	0.545
Graduated Diploma	4	4.1	24	24.7	18	18.5	46	47.3	
Graduated S1/S2/S3	6	6.2	27	27.9	14	14.5	47	48.6	
Total	10	10.3	55	56.7	32	33	97	100	

Table 3: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Education Level on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 3 shows the results of the cross tabulation that most of the respondents graduated from undergraduate (S1)/Masters (S2)/Doctoral (S3) with moderate performance as many as 27 people (27.9%). Statistical test results show the Spearman correlation test shows a p-value of 0.545, meaning that $p > 0.05$ means the test results are not significant. The results of statistical tests showed that there

was no influence between the level of education on the performance of employees at the RSGM, Jember University.

d) The Effect of Working Period on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The distribution of years of service shows that most of the respondents are 37 people (38.1%). The analysis of the effect of education level on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember will be presented in Table 4.

Variable	Not enough		Performance Currently		Well		Total		p -value
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Years of service									
<1 Year	0	0	0	0	2	2.1	2	2.1	0.036*
1-5 Years	4	4.1	17	17.5	16	16.5	37	38.1	
6-10 Years	2	2.1	22	22.7	8	8.2	32	33	
>10 Years	4	4.1	16	16.5	6	6.2	26	26.8	
Total	10	10.3	55	56.7	32	33	97	100	

Table 4: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Education Level on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 4 shows the results of the cross tabulation that most of the respondents with a working period of 6-10 years have moderate performance as many as 22 people (22.7%). Statistical test results show the Spearman correlation test shows a p-value of 0.036, meaning that $p < 0.05$ means the test results are significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between years of service on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

B. The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The distribution of leadership styles according to respondents shows that most of the leadership styles with a blend category between relationship and task orientation are 57 people (58.8%). The analysis of The Effect of leadership style on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember will be presented in Table 5.

Variable	Not enough		Performance				Total		p -value
	n	%	Currently	Well	n	%	n	%	
Leadership Style									
Relationship-oriented leadership	2	2.1	6	6.2	3	3.1	11	11.4	0.288
A mix of relationship and task orientation	5	5.1	35	36.1	17	17.5	57	58.7	
Task-oriented leadership	3	3.1	14	14.4	12	12.4	29	29.9	
Total	10	10.3	55	56.9	32	33	97	100	

Table 5: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 5 shows the results of the cross tabulation that most of the respondents stated that the leadership has a combination attitude between relationship and task orientation and has moderate performance as many as 35 people (36.1%). Statistical test results show the Spearman correlation test shows a p-value of 0.288, meaning that $p > 0.05$ means the test results are not significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is no influence between

leadership style on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

C. The Effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The distribution of work discipline shows that most of the respondents have moderate work discipline as many as 57 people (58.8%). The analysis of the effect of work discipline on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember will be presented in Table 6.

Variable	Not enough		Performance				Total		p -value
	n	%	Currently	Well	n	%	n	%	
Work Discipline									
Not enough	0	0	3	3.1	5	5.1	8	33	0.042*
Currently	6	6.1	31	37.2	20	20.6	57	58.8	
Well	4	4.1	21	21.6	7	7.3	32	8.2	
Total	10	10.2	55	61.8	32	33	97	100	

Table 6: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 6 shows the results of cross tabulation that most of the respondents with moderate work discipline have moderate performance as many as 31 people (37.2%). Statistical test results show the Spearman correlation test shows a p-value of 0.042, meaning that $p < 0.05$ means the test results are significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between work discipline on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

D. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The distribution of training shows that most of the respondents have a good category as many as 75 people (77.3%). The analysis of the effect of training on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember will be presented in Table 7.

Variable	Not enough		Performance				Total		p -value
	n	%	Currently	Well	n	%	n	%	
Training									
Not enough	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.009
Currently	2	2.1	19	19.5	1	1.1	22	22.7	
Well	8	8.3	36	37.1	31	31.9	75	77.3	
Total	10	10.4	55	56.6	32	33	97	100	

Table 7: Results of Analysis of the Effect of Training on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 7 shows the results of the cross tabulation that most of the good training had good performance as many as 36 people (37.1%). Statistical test results show the Spearman correlation test shows a p-value of 0.009, meaning that $p < 0.05$ means the test results are significant. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between training on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University.

E. The Most Influential Factors on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Table 8 will present a summary of the results of the analysis between variables for the multivariable analysis stage. Table 4.16 provides information that there are five independent variables that qualify as candidates for multivariable analysis. Variables that are considered eligible are those that have a p-value < 0.05 . Five variables that meet the requirements are included in the multivariable analysis stage to find out which variables have the most influence on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember.

No.	Variable	<i>p-value</i>	Information
1.	Gender	0.000*	Qualify
2.	Age	0.041*	Qualify
3.	Level of education	0.545	Not eligible
4.	Years of service	0.036*	Qualify
5.	Leadership style	0.288	Not eligible
6.	Work discipline	0.042*	Qualify
7.	Training	0.009*	Qualify

Table 8: Summary of Variable Results for the Multivariable Analysis Stage

Multivariable analysis was used to see the most influential factors on employee performance at RSGM Jember University. The results of the ordinal regression test analysis are presented in Table 9.

No.	Independent Variable	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>p-value</i>
1.	Work discipline	2.033	3,843	0.050*
2.	Training	-1,617	7,110	0.008*
3.	Age	-1.513	5,714	0.017*

Table 9: Results of Multivariable Analysis that Affect Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The results of the multivariable analysis in Table 9 show that there are three variables that have the most influence on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember. Conclusions from Table 9 are:

- The results of statistical tests using ordinal logistic regression tests on work discipline variables are 3.843 with a p-value of 0.050 and an estimate/OR value ($\text{Exp}(2.033) = 7.63$). This means that employees with good work discipline have a better performance of 7.63 times compared to employees with moderate and less disciplined work.
- The results of statistical tests using ordinal logistic regression test on the training variable are 7.110 with a p-value of 0.008 and an OR value ($\text{Exp}(-1.617) = 5.03$). This means that employees who have attended training well have better performance than respondents who have training, moderate and less.
- The results of statistical tests using ordinal logistic regression test on the age variable of 5.714 with a p-value of 0.017 and an OR value ($\text{Exp}(-1.513) = 4.54$). This means that employees aged between 31-40 years have a better performance of 4, 54 times compared to employees aged between 21 – 30 years and those aged >41 years.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Employee Characteristics (Gender, Age, Education and Years of Work) on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

a) Gender

Distribution of respondents by gender, some women and some men. This shows that based on women and men - men are balanced. In line with the research results of Hirarto and Sartika (2021) show that the distribution of the number of employees between men and women is the same. According to Saputri (2021) based on the upper echelon theory, each individual marked by gender has different characteristics in both performance and decision making. In theory, agencies that have female leaders are more likely to influence the company's performance and have an impact on the quality of the information produced. Meanwhile, according to Mulia in Wilda et al. (2018) gender differences

between men and women refer to emotional and spiritual elements, as a social characteristic in which the relationship between men and women is constructed so that it differs between place and time. The injustice experienced by women is associated with women having an emotional disposition so that women are not right to be leaders or managers in an agency. This is not in line with the theory proposed by Robbins in Awalia et al. (2021) stated that there was no gender difference between male and female in problem solving ability, analytical skills, competitive drive, motivation, sociality and learning ability. This is not in line with the theory proposed by Robbins in Awalia et al. (2021) stated that there was no gender difference between male and female in problem solving ability, analytical skills, competitive drive, motivation, sociality and learning ability. This is not in line with the theory proposed by Robbins in Awalia et al. (2021) stated that there was no gender difference between male and female in problem solving ability, analytical skills, competitive drive, motivation, sociality and learning ability. (Wilda, Sunaryo and Wahono, 2018; Awalia, Medyati and Giay, 2021; Hirarto et al., 2021; Saputri, 2021).

b) Age

The distribution by age shows most of them are between 31 – 40 years old. This shows that most of the respondents are of reproductive age to work so that it affects employee performance. Those who are still in their productive period usually have a higher level of productivity compared to workers who are old so that their physical possessions become weak and limited. (Aprilyanti, 2017; Harahap, 2019). This is in line with the research results of Awalia et al. (2021) shows the distribution analysis results, most of the respondents are aged 35 years compared to respondents aged >35 years. This is related to a decrease in performance with increasing age. According to Saputri (2021) age is classified into 3, namely early adulthood which is categorized as 18-40 years old, middle adulthood at 40-60 years old and elderly adults 60 years old until death. Middle adulthood is a time when a person maintains his career but is

also a time of increasing responsibility that must be carried out (Awalia, Medyati and Giay, 2021; Saputri, 2021).

According to stewardship theory, age is included in the criteria for developing the performance of an agency. The diversity of leaders can be classified in terms of age, ethnicity and gender. The number of members who sit on board seats in an agency is dominated by those who have entered the golden age group. According to Mayr (2011) the detrimental aspects of getting older can be compensated for from the knowledge, experience and wisdom gained from time to time and the negative aspects of getting older will be weakened due to the complexity of the work of a board member requiring special skills that must be possessed. (Ramadhani and Adhariani, no date; Mayr, 2011; Saputri, 2021).

c) Level of education

Distribution based on education level shows that most of the respondents graduated Bachelor (S1)/Master (S2)/Doctoral (S3) as many as 47 people and some of them graduated Diploma/equivalent. This shows that most of the employees have a good level of education. Education is a persuasive effort made to prepare students to be able to develop their potential as a whole in entering life in the future. The level of education is the stage of continuous education, which is determined based on the level of development of students, the level of complexity of teaching materials and the way in which teaching materials are presented (Dewi, Suwendra and Yulianthini, 2016; Harahap, 2019).

d) Years of service

The distribution based on years of service shows that some respondents have worked for 1 – 5 years and some have worked for 6 – 10 years. The period of work is a period of time or the length of time a worker has worked in an agency. A longer working period can affect employee motivation in improving performance. Term of service shows how long a person has worked in each job or position. A person's tenure can be related to the experience gained in the workplace, the longer a worker has the more experience and the higher his knowledge and skills. A longer working period indicates a person's more experience compared to other coworkers, so that more tenure. (Harahap, 2019).

B. The Effect of Respondent Characteristics (Gender, Age, Education Level and Years of Work) on Employee Performance at the RSGM University of Jember

a) The Effect of Gender on the Performance of RSGM Employees at the University of Jember

The results of the cross tabulation show that most of the women have moderate performance. The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between gender on employee performance at the RSGM Jember University. Similar research conducted by Wilda et al. (2018) shows that there is a significant effect on the performance of PT Beringin Gigantara KC Surabaya employees. These results indicate that between male and female employees have the same work behavior in completing their tasks, but the genders have different abilities in completing tasks that are considered heavy. The nature that is formed between men

and women is formed socially and culturally. Gender is not natural, but the roles of women and men are not constantly changing and can be exchanged, not biological in nature, but in the form of social culture that is constantly developing and improving. So it can be concluded that gender has an effect on employee performance (Wilda, Sunaryo and Wahono, 2018).

The results of the study are not in line with those of Prasastin (2013), there is no relationship between gender and the performance of malaria epidemiological surveillance officers with the performance of malaria epidemiological surveillance officers at the puskesmas level. Another study conducted by Syamsuriansyah et al. (2020) showed that there was no effect between gender and the performance of medical record officers at private hospitals in Mataram City. Performance is a commitment choice chosen by officers, not an innate characteristic. Each gender, both male and female, has their respective abilities in implementing performance (Syamsuriansyah et al., 2021).

b) The Effect of Age on the Employee Performance of RSGM Jember University

The results of the cross tabulation show that most of the respondents aged 31-40 years have moderate performance. Statistical test results show that there is an influence between age on employee performance at the RSGM Universitas Jember. In line with Harahap's research (2019), there is a significant correlation between age and the performance of employees participating in training at BPSDM DKI Jakarta Province. Age is the length of time living or existing since birth or being held. Age also affects a person's psyche where a young age often causes tension, confusion, anxiety and fear so that it can affect his behavior. As they get older, they tend to be more aware of and know about the real problem. The older you get, the more experience you get. (Harahap, 2019).

At the age of 25-44, a person has established himself in the job he has chosen and is no longer interested in changing jobs if the situation is not pressed. Age 45-60 a person (employee or employee) begins to pursue and improve the quality of work or duties and responsibilities entrusted by the institution or organization where he works. Age is a factor that plays a role in performance. Older employees will be experienced in completing their work compared to younger employees, but younger employees tend to be more sensitive, open and more flexible to changes and new things. (Megawati and K., 2014). There are limitations regarding age which have no effect on employee performance.

c) The Effect of Education Level on Employee Performance of RSGM Jember University

The results of the cross tabulation show that most of the graduates (S1)/Masters (S2)/Doctorate (S3) have moderate performance. The results of statistical tests showed that there was no influence between the level of education on the performance of employees at the RSGM, Jember University. In line with the research of Mandang et al. (2017) showed that there was no influence between the level of education on the performance of employees at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Manado Branch. This means

that every increase in employee performance is not influenced by the level of education of an employee. This is because the level of education of an employee does not guarantee employee performance. Employees with various educational levels will continue to work optimally according to scientific disciplines so that performance will increase or be maintained. Education plays an important role as a basic need for many companies or agencies that will accept someone to work according to their level of education. Higher education will be easier to get a job, on the other hand someone with low education has fewer doors open for a better career. Human resources or employees who occupy certain positions in the organization do not necessarily have the abilities that match the requirements of the position (Mandang, Lumanauw and Walangitan, 2017).

The results of this study are not in line with the research of Wirawan et al. (2019) states that there is a positive influence between the level of education on employee performance at PT Mandiri Tri Makmur. According to Wirawan et al. (2019) states that a person's level of education will affect employee performance. The high level of employee education affects the ability to achieve optimal performance. According to Harahap (2019), it shows that along with a good level of education, it is directly proportional to an increase in performance as long as the ability to work also increases. Along with having the ability, employees can carry out their duties and responsibilities properly, on time and produce satisfactory performance. According to Lestari in Putri et al. (2019) states that the level of education is an activity of a person in developing his abilities, attitudes, and forms of behavior, both for future life where through certain organizations or not organized. Meanwhile, according to the language center of the national education department, education is a process of changing the attitudes and procedures of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through efforts and training. (Harahap, 2019; Putri and Ratnasari, 2019; Wirawan, Bagia and Susila, 2019).

d) The Effect of Working Period on the Employee Performance of RSGM Jember University

The results of the cross tabulation show that 6-10 years of service have moderate performance. The results of statistical tests indicate that there is an influence between years of service on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University. The results of this study are in line with the research of Harahap (2019) which shows that there is a relationship between years of service and the performance of DKI Jakarta civil servants who attend training at BPSDM DKI Jakarta Province. The period of service is a time that is calculated from the start of an employee working until the collection of research data. The working period is often a measure to determine a person's maturity at work. The longer a person's working period, the more mature they will be in mastering the work that is their expertise as indicated by better productivity/performance (Asmuji, 2018; Harahap, 2019). Workers/employees will be more empowered, which can be caused by increased experience, namely in terms of the length of service a worker has taken. In addition, with increasing years of service, workers will increasingly develop and master their work (Laminia et al., 2018).

Another inconsistent study conducted by Laminia and Muniroh (2018) shows that there is no effect between years of service and the productivity/performance of workers in the home industry. The results of the research show that the longer the working period of a respondent, does not describe a significant relationship to his work productivity. Likewise, respondents with a short working period also do not describe a relationship. This happens because the respondent's work concentration is still less focused on a definite job so that it cannot describe the relationship between tenure and work productivity (Laminia et al., 2018).

C. *The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember*

The distribution based on leadership style shows that most of the leadership styles are in the blend category between relationship and task orientation and some are in the category of task-oriented leadership. Leadership style is a pattern of behavior favored by the leader in the process of directing and influencing employees. Every leader likes his own leadership style. The leader can carry out his job well if the leader can adapt to the work situation he faces, whereas if the employee does not perform well, it is difficult for the company organization to get good results. (Coal, 2020).

This requires the leadership to use the authority to change the attitudes and behavior of employees to want to work hard and want to achieve optimal results. To influence the desired employee attitudes and behavior, the leader must improve the desired employee performance, the leader must improve employee performance in order to encourage employees to work well. The company's success is basically supported by its effective leadership, which with that leadership can influence subordinates to raise their work motivation to participate in common goals. A leader is a person who applies principles and techniques that ensure motivation, discipline, and productivity when working with people, tasks, and situations to achieve organizational goals. (Coal, 2020).

The results of statistical tests show that there is no influence between leadership style on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University. The results of the recapitulation based on respondents' answers mostly show that the attitude of the leadership at RSGM is oriented towards the relationship between tasks and subordinates. This means that a good and open leadership attitude towards employees already supports employee performance, only needs to be studied from other factors that affect performance. This is in line with research conducted by Rosalina and Wati (2020) which shows that there is no influence between leadership style on employee performance. The results of his research show that leadership style has no effect on employee performance because there are many other factors that affect employee performance (Rosalina et al., 2020). According to Siagian and Khair (2018) an increase in the value of leadership style will be followed by an increase in performance value, but the increase in performance is not in line with expectations or is too low. This problem can be seen in the condition of the leadership style that has not been able to direct (act as a motivator)

towards its employees and lack a firm stance (assertiveness) in carrying out all regulations for employees. This situation has an impact on employee performance in terms of achieving better quality performance, achieving quantity of performance, sense of responsibility for a job, employee's ability to innovate and take initiative at work.(Siagian and Khair, 2018).

The results of this study are not in line with those of Ahmad and Thamrin (2021) showing a significant influence between leadership style on employee performance at PT. Pelindo IV (PERSERO) Makassar Branch. An agency basically expects maximum employee performance. Because with good employee performance, of course, the performance of the agency/company will be good and can achieve the existing targets. According to him, one of the factors associated with improving employee performance is one's leadership style. With such a leadership style is able to determine and affect the performance of the employee. So that the applied leadership style can be used as an evaluation of whether employee performance and organizational performance will increase or even decrease. According to Sadriah (2016) the leadership style set by a manager in the organization can create a harmonious integration and encourage employee enthusiasm to achieve maximum goals. Meanwhile, according to Sutrisno (2017) that company leaders must be guided by leadership theories, so that leaders in companies have the ability to influence and motivate employees which have an impact on improving performance.(Sadariah, 2016; Sutrisno, 2017; Ahmad and Thamrin, 2021).

Based on some of the results of the research above, it can be concluded that leadership style is a set of characteristics or methods used by a leader to influence subordinates so that organizational goals can be achieved. Therefore, the leadership style that plays an active role in the success of the organization in carrying out various activities is mainly seen in the performance of its employees. Effective and efficient results of a leader can be seen from how a leader himself influences his subordinates, how the pattern is used to communicate and cooperate with his employees. Meanwhile, employee performance is the result of work and responsibilities that have been achieved and implemented by employees both in quality and quantity(Ahmad and Thamrin, 2021).

D. The Effect of Work Discipline on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Distribution based on work discipline shows that most of the respondents have moderate work discipline and some have good categories. The results showed that in RSGM, most of the employees' work discipline was still moderate, this is in line with secondary data that has been studied by researchers related to work discipline which shows that most of the employees have come late to work. Work discipline includes employee awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable organizational regulations and social norms. Thus, work discipline is a tool used by leaders to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change their behavior to follow the rules set by the agency. Discipline must be enforced in an organization. It means,

without the support of good employee discipline, it is difficult for the organization to realize its goals. So discipline is the key to the success of an organization in achieving its goals(Lijan, 2017).

The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between work discipline on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University. This is in line with the results of research by Arrizy et al. (2021) shows that there is an influence between work discipline on employee performance at PT. Brataco Surabaya Branch. Another research conducted by Ardiana et al. (2021) shows that there is an influence between work discipline on employee performance at PT. Yuwana by Catur Manunggal Sisdoarjo. One of the factors that affect employee performance is work discipline. According to Simamora (2015) discipline is a procedure that corrects or punishes subordinates for violating rules or procedures.(Simamora, 2015; Ardiana, Sutopo and Istanti, 2021; Arrizky, Budiarto and Prasetyo, 2021).

The results of other research conducted by Ariana (2013) show that there is no effect of work discipline on employee performance. In his research, it is stated that companies/agencies can pay more attention to employee abilities, remuneration for employees, sanctions for disciplinary violations, tighter supervision in an effort to improve or improve employee performance. These things prove that work discipline is an important factor in improving employee performance. With good work discipline from employees such as arriving on time, carrying out work in accordance with what has been determined by the company, obeying company regulations, it will be able to improve the performance of these employees so that the agency's targets will be achieved.(Ariana and Riana, 2013).

E. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

Distribution based on training shows that most of the respondents have good categories and some have sufficient categories. Training is a shared responsibility between employees and the organization. Employees are obliged to design and participate in job training to develop their abilities so that a better career will be opened up in the future(Lijan, 2017). According to Gomes (2013), training is useful for overcoming the lack of knowledge and skills possessed by employees(Gomes, 2013).

The results of statistical tests show that there is an influence between training on employee performance at the RSGM University of Jember. In line with Gumilar's (2015) research, training has a significant effect on employees' work ability. This is in accordance with Mangkunegara's (2015) research. One of the factors that can affect the achievement of performance is the ability factor. Based on Rivai's theory (2015) shows that performance is a function of ability. According to Hasibuan (2017) the training method must be based on job requirements depending on various factors, namely time, cost, number of participants, participant's basic education level, peer background, and others. This shows that by improving a good or appropriate training method, it will also improve the employee's performance(Gumilar, 2015;

Mangkunegara and Prabu, 2015; Rivai, 2015; Hasibuan, 2017; Arrizky, Budiarto and Prasetyo, 2021).

Training is a teaching and learning process using certain techniques and methods conceptually which is intended to improve the skills and work abilities of a person or group of people. Training is held by an agency that aims to improve and develop the attitudes, behavior, skills and knowledge of employees according to the wishes of the relevant agency. If employees have been trained, they will have better abilities and skills, so that they are able to work more effectively and efficiently, and in the end these employees achieve good performance as well. (Saefulloh and Ekowati, 2021).

The results of this study are not in line with the research of Ginting et al. (2020) shows that there is no significant effect between training on employee performance at PT Dami Mas Sejahtera Kampar Riau. According to him, training has not become a variable that affects employee performance, because the training provided to employees will have the same impact, because not all employees receive training. So that not all employees can feel the impact of the training (Ginting, Pelawi and Syahriani, 2020).

F. The Most Influential Factors on Employee Performance at RSGM Universitas Jember

The results of the analysis using the ordinal logistic regression test showed that the independent variable that became the most influential determinant of employee performance at RSGM Jember University was work discipline with the highest OR value of 7.63. The results of this study are supported by Syafrina's research (2016) discipline is the most important operative function of human resource management, the better the employee's work discipline, the higher the work performance that can be achieved. Without good employee work discipline, it is difficult for an organization to achieve optimal results, so discipline is the key to the success of a company in achieving its goals (Syafrina, 2016).

Good discipline reflects a person's sense of responsibility towards the tasks assigned to him. This encourages enthusiasm for work, enthusiasm for work, and the realization of the goals of the company and its employees. Therefore, the leader tries to make his subordinates always have good discipline. Leaders are said to be effective in their leadership, if their subordinates are well disciplined. To maintain and improve good discipline is a difficult thing, because many factors influence it. Discipline must be enforced in a company organization. Without the support of good employee discipline, the company will find it difficult to realize its goal of achieving optimal performance. So, discipline is the key to the success of a company in achieving its goals (Syafrina, 2016).

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study concluded the following things; 1) Distribution of respondent characteristics, leadership style, work discipline and training and performance, including: a). Gender distribution shows that most of the respondents are female and some are male;

b). The distribution by age shows that most of the respondents are between 31 – 40 years old, some are >41 years old and between 21 – 30 years old; c). The distribution of education level shows that most of them graduated from bachelor (S1)/Master (S2)/Doctorate (S3) and some others graduated from diploma/equivalent; d). The distribution of years of service shows that most of the respondents have served between 1 -5 years and some of them have worked between 6 – 10 years; e). The distribution of leadership styles shows that most of the leadership styles are categorized as a mix between relationship and task orientation and some are task-oriented leaders; f). The distribution of work discipline shows that most of the respondents have moderate work discipline and some have good work discipline; g). The distribution of training shows that most of the respondents have good training and some have moderate training; h). The distribution of performance shows that most of the respondents have good performance, while others have good performance; 2) The results of the analysis of the characteristics of the respondents indicate that there is an influence between gender, age and years of service on the performance of employees at RSGM Jember University. There is no influence between the level of education on the performance of employees at the RSGM Jember University; 3) The results of the analysis of leadership styles show that there is no effect on employee performance at the RSGM, Jember University; 4) The results of the work discipline analysis show that there is an influence on the performance of employees at the RSGM Universitas Jember; 5) The results of the training analysis show that there is an influence on the performance of employees at the RSGM Universitas Jember; 6) The most influential factor on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University is work discipline. 5) The results of the training analysis show that there is an influence on the performance of employees at the RSGM Universitas Jember; 6) The most influential factor on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University is work discipline. 5) The results of the training analysis show that there is an influence on the performance of employees at the RSGM Universitas Jember; 6) The most influential factor on the performance of the employees of RSGM Jember University is work discipline.

Recommendations that can be given are 1) For leaders and employees, leaders should be more oriented towards subordinates, based on research results showing that leadership orientation is more inclined towards tasks and employees should be open to always growing in improving service quality both in knowledge and skills; 2) For Agencies, there are sanctions, both written and verbal, for leaders and employees if they do not apply good work discipline. In addition to providing sanctions, it is necessary to provide rewards for employees who achieve performance targets. This is a consequence for quality institutions in public services by basing performance on Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and re-evaluating the training achievements obtained by employees whether they are in accordance with the minimum training standards:

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